

Supplemental Results:

Dependence of Pack Life Time on Maximal Lag Time:

For analyzing the effect of cell density on the evolution of collective motion on GBM cells, the 20 h measurement frame was subdivided into 6 h time-windows ($\tau_{win\ 6h}$). Thereby we denoted that the averaged measured pack life times of the 6 h time windows ($\tau_{life\ 6h}$) did not match those of the 20 h measurements ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$), if they are not significantly smaller than the maximal lag time (6h). Roughly identical results were only obtained for pack lifetimes up to 1/3 of the used window time (120 min). Afterwards, the deviation increased non-linearly with the pack lifetime observed in the 20 h measurements (Fig S4 g). Plotting the pack life time measured in the 6 h time window normalized to the 20 h values ($\tau_{life\ 6h}/\tau_{life\ 20h}$) over the inverse true pack life time from the 20 h time window normalized to the 6 h time frame ($\tau_{win\ 6h}/\tau_{life\ 20h}$) an exponential decay ($R^2 = 0.94$) was found, supporting the previous observation (Fig S4 h). To evaluate the minimal time window to reliably measure pack lifetime the mean pack lifetime (τ_{life}) of LN229 cells for varying maximal lag times (τ_{win}) of 30 min to 20 h was measured. Afterwards, the maximal lag time over the mean measured lifetimes was plotted. Both values were normalized to the lifetime of the 20 h measurements ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$, Fig S4 i). Thereby we observed, similar to our initial observation, that for reliably measuring pack lifetime (deviation <5%) the chosen time-window needs to be at least 2.5 times larger than the actual pack lifetime.

Supplementary Tables:

Table S1:

Table S1: Comparison of methods used for estimation of cell-cell adhesion.

	AFM	Fluorescence Labeling	Spheroid Aggregation
Time Scale	1 min	Equilibrium	Equilibrium
Type of Measurement	Direct	Indirect	Indirect
Ratio to CTL			
LN229 + Y-27632	0.788	0.263	0.166
LN229 + Blebbistatin	0.925	0.354	0.334
U138 + Y-27632	0.824	0.397	0.444
U138 + Blebbistatin	0.573	0.443	0.561

Supplementary Figures:

Fig S1:

Fig S2:

Fig S3:

Fig S4:

Fig S5:

Fig S6:

Fig S7:

Fig S8:

Fig S9:

Fig S10:

Fig S11:

Fig S12:

Fig S13:

Supplemental Figure Legends:

Fig S1: Time evolution of the order parameter Q . Order parameter Q for astrocytes and the two GBM cell lines for the 20 h time window. Shaded areas correspond to standard errors of the mean. Sample sizes are identical to figure 2.

Fig S2: Shape factor and neighborhood for astrocytes in different seeding densities and for different treatments at defined time points. a) Conserved neighborhood for different seeding densities of astrocytes. b) illustrates the shape factor for different seeding densities and c) for treatment with the ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 or myosin II inhibitor blebbistatin. The dotted line shows the critical value of 3.81 predicted by the vertex model. Below cells are considered to be jammed. Box plots show the median (red line), 25 and 75 percentile (box), non-outlier range (whiskers) and outliers (red dots).

Fig S3: Shape factor of GBM cells over time after ROCK or myosin II inhibition. a) Shape factor for LN229 or b) U138 cells when treated with the ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 or myosin II inhibitor blebbistatin at defined time points. The dotted line shows the critical value of 3.81 predicted by the vertex model. Below cells are considered to be jammed. Box plots show the median (red line), 25 and 75 percentile (box), non-outlier range (whiskers) and outliers (red dots).

Fig S4: Order parameter and 4-point susceptibility over time. a)-c) Order parameter of astrocytes, LN229 and U138 glioblastoma cells at different time points, using a 6 h window. d)-f) Show the corresponding 4-point susceptibilities. g) Measured pack life time for all cell types and treatments using the 20 h time window ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$) over the time measured when using the 6 h time window ($\tau_{life\ 6h}$). h) Plot of the pack life time of the 6 h window ($\tau_{life\ 6h}$) divided by the values of the 20 h measurement ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$) over the inverse of the pack lifetime in the 20 h time window ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$), normalized to the window size ($\tau_{win\ 6h}$). The red dotted line shows a fit of an exponential decay. i) Exemplary evolution of the measured pack lifetime (τ_{life}) normalized

to pack lifetime measured for the 20 h time window ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$) as a function of the length of the time window (τ_{win}) in units of the pack lifetime for the 20 h window ($\tau_{life\ 20h}$) for LN229 cells. a-f,i) Shaded areas and error bars correspond to standard errors of the mean. Sample sizes are identical to figure 1.

Fig S5: Long-term measurements of collective migration. The panels depict a) average layer speed, b) order parameter and c) 4-point susceptibility for astrocytes, LN229 and U138 cells for a period of 60 h. d-f) Plot of the layer reorganization in terms of conserved neighborhood calculated for individual 20 h intervals. g) Amount of preserved neighborhood for all three cell types for the whole measurement time. a-c) Error bars and shaded areas depict the standard error of the mean. d-g) Box plots show the median (red line), 25 and 75 percentile (box), non-outlier range (whiskers) and outliers (red dots).

Fig S6: Analysis of single cell motility. Effect of ROCK and myosin II inhibition on a) directional persistence and b) movement speed of single cells of astrocytes, LN229 and U138. Box plots show the median (red line), 25 and 75 percentile (box), non-outlier range (whiskers) and outliers (red dots).

Fig S7: Plot of the typical paths for LN229 and U138 GBM cells. a) and b) show typical paths for LN229 and U138 GBM cells when treated with the ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 or myosin II inhibitor blebbistatin.

Fig S8: Velocity auto-correlation length as function speed and cell density. Plot of the velocity auto-correlation length for astrocytes, LN229 and U138 cells as a) function of time and b) speed. c-e) Depiction of the velocity auto-correlation length for astrocytes, LN229 and U138 cells as a function of cell density. a) shaded areas depict the standard error of the mean.

Fig S9: Number of stress fibers per cell in astrocytes, LN229 and U138 GBM cells when treated with the ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 or myosin II inhibitor blebbistatin. Box plots show the

median (red line), 25 and 75 percentile (box), non-outlier range (whiskers) and outliers (red dots).

Fig S10: Representative images of n-cadherin and β -catenin staining. a) demonstrates the presence of N-cadherin in LN229 and U138 cells at cell-cell-contact sites. b) Enlargement of Fig 7a to illustrate the discontinuous, punctuated pattern of β -catenin at cell-cell-contact sites after ROCK or myosin II inhibition. Arrows highlight regions with a highly punctuated pattern. Scale bars depict 10 μ m.

Fig S11: Representative images of β -catenin staining for astrocytes and U138 cells. Scale bars depict 10 μ m.

Fig S12: Plot of the adhesion and spheroid aggregation of astrocytes and LN229 and U138 GBM cells when treated with the ROCK inhibitor Y-27632 or myosin II inhibitor blebbistatin. a-c) Plot of the mean cell-cell-adhesion energies over time for the three cell types and treatments used. Final adhesion energies were obtained after reaching the equilibrium/plateau. d-e) Plot of the relative brightness of the spheroid over time for the three cell types and treatments used. a-f) Sample sizes are identical to figure 7d. g-i) Representative spheroid images at the beginning and end of each measurement for each cell type and treatment. Scale bars depict 300 μ m.

Fig S13: Experimental setup for the used types of atomic force microscopy experiments. The first column shows the setup for measuring the cortex tension of single cells, the second column the setup for determination of the Young's modulus of a cell monolayer and the third depicts the setup for assessing cell-cell adhesion.

Supplementary Video Legends:

Supplementary Vid S1: Astrocytes imaged every 3 min over 20 h.

Supplementary Vid S2: LN229 cells imaged every 3 min over 20 h.

Supplementary Vid S3: U138 cells imaged every 3 min over 20 h.